

SHORT NOTES

Organic Compounds of Lanthanide Elements: Preparation of Acylates of Praseodymium and Neodymium

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In an earlier publication¹, the preparation of tri-laurates, palmitates, and stearates of lanthanum and cerium (III) has been described and these have been shown to be non-hydrolysable, stable compounds. Similar derivatives of praseodymium and neodymium have been obtained and some new compounds are described in this communication.

Sodium salts of the fatty acids (lauric, palmitic, and stearic) were found to react quantitatively with aqueous solutions of praseodymium and neodymium chlorides, as with lanthanum and cerium (III), with instantaneous precipitation of light green and light pink solids.

(where M = praseodymium or neodymium and R = C₁₁H₂₃, C₁₅H₃₁, and C₁₇H₃₅).

The reaction mixtures were heated to flocculate the precipitate. After cooling to the room temperature, the precipitates were filtered and washed thoroughly with water, followed by ethanol. After being dried first in an air oven and then under reduced pressure, the products were found to correspond in analysis to tri-acylates.

Finally pure samples were obtained by crystallising them from their benzene solutions. The tri-acylates provided viscous solutions when dissolved in benzene and addition of water appeared to have no appreciable effect on the viscosities of their solutions. These findings are of interest in view of the considerable work done on viscometric behaviour of aluminium acylates^{3,4}. These tri-acylates appeared to melt at a lower temperature, but a correct observation of the melting points could not be made due to long melting range.

The preparation and properties of hydrated and anhydrous rare earth acetates have been extensively investigated by different workers^{5,6}. The reactions of anhydrous lanthanum and cerium (III) chlorides with acetic acid and acetic anhydride yielded tri-acetates which were found to be monomeric in benzene in these laboratories⁶.

1. Misra *et al.*, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, 25, 195.
2. *Idem, ibid.*, 1963, 25, 201.
3. McRoberts and Schulman, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1950, A200, 136.
4. Legar *et al.*, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1957, 35, 799.
5. Ryatchikov and Vagina, *Zhur. Neorg. Khim.*, 1960, 5, 356.
6. Seaton *et al.*, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1955, 9, 222.

Similar reactions were carried out with anhydrous praseodymium and neodymium chlorides with acetic acid, acetic anhydride-acetic acid mixture, and acetic anhydride alone. Reactions, which were carried out by refluxing for several hours with acetic acid alone, were most facile and quick and those with acetic anhydride were rather slow. On completion of the reactions, the products were filtered, washed repeatedly with acetic acid, and dried under reduced pressure and at elevated temperature (60-65°).

In all these reactions light green crystalline tri-acetate of praseodymium and light pink crystalline tri-acetate of neodymium were the final products in quantitative yield. Neodymium acetate was found to be more soluble than praseodymium acetate and it could be separated as fine crystals only after leaving the clear mother liquor for about 48 hr. The reaction of neodymium chloride with acetic acid was faster than praseodymium chloride or than that of lanthanum and cerium (III) anhydrous chlorides with acetic acid². The tri-acetates are sparingly soluble. Their molecular weight measurements, carried out ebullioscopically in benzene, show them to be monomeric. These tri-acetates are readily soluble in water and do not exhibit a pronounced tendency of hydrolysis in aqueous solutions.

Study of absorption spectra of neodymium acetate in water has been made and the results obtained are in conformity with the observations of Seaton *et al*⁶. The method of preparation is similar to those used in our previous works^{5,12}, and thus for brevity are summarised below.

TABLE I

Products.	Colour.	% Metal.		% Acyloxy.		M. Wt.	
		Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Pr(OOCC ₁₁ H ₂₃) ₃	Light green	18.9	19.12	81.0	80.88		
Nd(OOCC ₁₁ H ₂₃) ₃	Do	19.3	19.44	80.1	80.56		
Pr(OOCC ₁₃ H ₃₁) ₃	Do	15.5	15.52	83.6	84.48		
Nd(OOCC ₁₃ H ₃₁) ₃	Light pink	15.9	15.85	83.2	84.15		
Pr(OOCC ₁₇ H ₃₅) ₃	Light green	14.0	14.18	84.0	85.82		
Nd(OOCC ₁₇ H ₃₅) ₃	Light pink	14.6	14.50	84.2	85.50		
Pr(OOCC ₃ H ₇) ₃	Green	44.5	43.98	55.8	55.02	321	308
Nd(OOCC ₃ H ₇) ₃	Pink	44.6	44.89	56.5	55.11	329	311

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